

Experimental Investigation of the Hydrodynamic and Oxygenation Performance of Flapping-Based Aerator

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This study investigated the hydrodynamic and oxygenation efficacy of a flapping-based aerator, using the SonTek Acoustic Doppler Velocimeter (ADV) to analyse the velocity profile and flow dynamics. This aerator incorporates a NACA0017 aerofoil, producing thrust by flapping motions, resulting in a reverse von Kármán vortex street, which harvests the wake energy for the rotation of airfoils. The main objective was to characterize the aerator's velocity distribution, turbulence intensity, and oxygenation efficiency in an aqueous environment. The Acoustic Doppler Velocimeter quantified flow velocity components over all three axes in different depths of regions to better understand flow features, including jet-like flows and vertical mixing. Experiments were conducted to examine their impact on hydrodynamic performance by adjusting operating factors, including flapping frequency, amplitude, and submergence depth.

Additionally, this study measured dissolved oxygen (DO) levels using a DO sensor to assess the aerator's efficiency in oxygenation. The results reveal that a flapping-based aerator increased the DO level more rapidly than a porous microbubble diffuser alone. The NACA0017 airfoil-driven flapping mechanism generates thrust and induces extensive flow circulation, enhancing mixing and aeration efficiency. Therefore, the measured dissolved oxygen levels rise. These findings suggest the economic feasibility of flapping-based aerators as sustainable and efficient solutions in aquaculture, wastewater treatment, and environmental remediation. All the results will be thoroughly discussed in the presentation.

Figure 1. (a) X velocity vs time, (b) Y velocity vs time and (c) Z velocity vs time

Figure 2. (a) RMS velocity vs Depth, (b) Turbulence Intensity vs Depth and (c) TKE vs Depth

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¹ Anderson et al., *Journal of Fluid mechanics*, **360**, 41–72 (1998)

² Boyd et al., *The Progressive Fish-Culturist*, **48(1)**, 68–70 (1986)